

Effect of Impact Angle on Slurry Erosion Corrosion behavior of Extruded NiAl-Bronze Deposited over Cast NiAl-Bronze by Friction Surfacing

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Abstract – Cast nickel-aluminum bronze (NAB) alloy is a material which is specified for most of the marine applications and propellers of ship, because of its exceptional corrosion-resistance joined with tolerable mechanical properties. However, the corrosion-erosion resistance of Cast nickel-aluminum bronze (NAB) alloy is relatively not good as wrought nickel-aluminum bronze alloy. Hence, in this research an effort has been taken to improve the corrosion-erosion resistance of cast nickel-aluminum bronze alloy deposit wrought (extruded) NAB alloy by friction surface technique. Erosion-corrosion tests have been carried out on slurries mixed with sand particles of having 3.5 % NaCl solution. Silica sand is having a average size range of 250–355 μm is used as an erodent. The specimens were tested at 30° & 90° impingement angle. It is observed that the erosion-corrosion resistance of friction surfaced NAB alloy exhibited improved resistance than cast NAB alloy. SEM analysis showed that the erosion tracks developed in the cast NAB alloy were wider and deeper than that formed over the friction surfaced extruded NAB alloy.

Keywords: Friction, Microstructure, Surfacing, Erosion, Corrosion

I. Introduction

From old times, various methods such as plating, deposition and spraying have been attempted and commercialized to surface modify materials. Each of these methods, however, involves complex procedures and requires numerous processes [1]. The friction surfacing is a potential surface modification method, the principle of which is relatively simple, with which coating would be enabled after rebuilt of friction welding machines [2]. This method is superior with respect to resource and energy conservation. Also, most coating methods used for repairing castings consist of arc or gas welding therefore, the type of materials used limits applicable coating materials [3]. On the other hand, based on the fact that friction surfacing, whose procedure is similar to the principle of friction welding, is a form of solid state bonding, a wide variety of combinations of materials are possible, and additional function might be given to surfacing[4]. Surfacing can be done at low temperatures because surface modification takes place in the solid phase; therefore, minimal thermal effects on the materials can be anticipated [5]. Solid state processing technologies are now readily available and reliable alternatives to the conventional processes [6]. Friction surfacing is a capable new technology for depositing metallurgical bonded coatings on engineering components to resist wear and corrosion [7]. Being a solid state process, friction surfacing reduces the problems such as porosity, hot cracking, segregation, and dilution which are generally associated with fusion-based techniques [8]. This is achieved because no melting is done in this process. The process is started by pressing a rotating stud made from the coating material onto the

substrate with a defined pressure. Due to frictional heating the strength of the stud material declines and the resulting torsional force causes plastic shear deformation. Now a translational movement is applied, in the course of which material from the plasticized stud is deposited over the substrate [9]. The selected traverse and rotational speed, as well as the normal pressure are the main influences on width and thickness of the coating layer and the bonding quality [10]. In the present research coatings were generated from NiAl-bronze, as used for maritime components and pumps, on self-mating substrate. NiAl-bronzes are usually selected for their good corrosion properties in sea water, their resistance against cavitation erosion (E.g. for ship propellers) and their adequate mechanical properties [11]. It was shown that the achieved homogeneity and the fine grained microstructure are advantageous for the mechanical properties of the bronze, and that small voids and casting defects near the surface can be closed [12]. From the literature review, very few published information available on the erosion corrosion performance of friction surfaced coatings in NAB, the corrosion behavior of the material in various forms has been widely studied because of its industrial significance.

II. Materials and Experimental Methods

II.1. Friction surfacing of NiAl-bronze

Friction surfacing was implemented with the studs of 20 mm diameter and 70 mm length, on plates having dimensions of 150 mm×150 mm×10 mm. The chemical composition of the materials used is given in the Table 1. The substrate was prepared for surfacing process by

grinding with 120- grit abrasive paper and degreasing with acetone. A fully computer numerical controlled (CNC) friction stir welding (FSW) machine was used to do the welds. Surfacing parameters were 200 mm/min traverse speed, 60 mm/min plunge rate and a rotational speed of the studs of 2500 rpm. Single layer surfacing has been performed. The coating produced by the friction surfacing sample of deposition stage and coating is shown in Fig.1 (a & b).

TABLE 1
CHEMICAL COMPOSITION CAST % OF SUBSTRATE AND MECHTRODE MATERIAL

Element	Cu	Al	Ni	Fe	Mn	Si
Substrate	81.6	10.10	3.78	4.01	0.30	0.16 (max)
Mechtrode	80.9	10.20	3.77	4.6	0.27	0.17

II.2. Slurry erosion test

Slurry erosion tests have been performed in specially designed rig and it is shown in Fig.2. This test rig enables testing at different sets of parameters. It has integral flexibility through which the impact velocity (v), the angle of impingement (h), the mass flux rate (m), the particle size (S) the distribution (d), and stand-off distance between nozzle outlet and target surface could be individually controlled. The rig is constructed on a design known as non-recirculating type which simulates the real working environment of the fluid machineries specifically turbines and pumps.

Slurry erosion testing has been conducted in accordance with the procedure given in ASTM G-73. Specimens were cut in to the size of 10 mm diameter 10 mm thick by using wire cut EDM. Samples were polished with 2500 grid emery papers over the roughly finished surface. The samples prepared for slurry erosion corrosion for substrate and friction surfaced samples are shown in Fig.3. Preceding to testing all the samples, coated as well as uncoated were grounded using emery papers down to 1500 grit size. Thereafter, they were polished using 1 μm alumina slurry paste on disk polishing machine. Mass loss measurements were also performed using precision weighing balance of an accuracy of 0.0001mg. After test initially there is an increase in weight due to the addition of corrosion products so in order to remove that samples were washed with water combined with conc. HCL acid solution in the ratio of 2:1 and dried in air before weight measurements.

III. Results

III.1. Erosion and Corrosion

The weight-loss of the substrate and friction surfaced samples as a function of the impact angle in the presence of slurry is measured. It is noted that when the impact angle increased from 30° to 90° the weight-loss is increased. Erosion rate is the difference between sample

weights before test with the sample weight after test. Corrosion rate is calculated from the formulae (Eq.1) and erosion and corrosion rate for base metal for 30° and 90° angle of impact is given in Tables 2 & 3. Figs 4 (a&b) shows the effect of impact angle on erosion corrosion of friction surfaced NAB material. From the Fig 4, it is observed that in both charts the erosion rate and corrosion rate increases at 90° compared with 30°. For the base metal corrosion and erosion rate increases when compared with coated samples (Fig. 4 b).

$$\text{Corrosion rate} = (K \times W) / (A \times T \times D) \tag{1}$$

Corrosion rate is measured in mm per year (mm/y)

Where $K =$ a constant (8.76×10^4)

$T =$ time of exposure in hours (1hr)

$A =$ area in cm^2 ,

$W =$ mass loss in grams, and

$D =$ density in g/cm^3 ($8.94 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$)

TABLE 2
EROSION AND CORROSION RATE OF SUBSTRATE (BASE METAL) MATERIAL (CAST NAB ALLOY)

S.No	Angle (deg)	Base metal weight Before test (g)	Base metal weight after test(g)	Mass Loss (g)	Corrosion rate (mm/y)
1	30	4.6559	4.6534	0.0025	25.7771
2	90	4.3510	4.3422	0.0088	90.7355

TABLE 3
EROSION AND CORROSION RATE OF COATING MATERIAL- FRICTION SURFACED DEPOSIT (EXTRUDED NAB ALLOY)

S.No	Angle (deg)	Coated metal weight Before test (g)	Coated metal weight After test (g)	Mass Loss (g)	Corrosion rate (mm/y)
1	30	3.8997	3.8982	0.0015	15.4662
2	90	3.7395	3.7317	0.0078	80.4246

III.2. Optical microstructure

Fig.5(a) – 5(c) show the optical micrographs of the substrate (cast NAB), mechatrode (Extruded NAB) and friction surfaced interface zone. The cast NAB material has a dual phase structure which contains martensite and α phase (Fig.5 a). Tool material shows (Mechatrode) Widmanstatten pattern of microstructure (Fig.5 b). The microstructure inside one coating layer comprises lamellar as well as globular α grains, enclosed by quenched β phase. Close to the surface of the layer, the phase is of lamellar shape (Fig.5 c).

After erosion corrosion test the damaged surfaces of the specimens were examined by optical microscopy as shown in Fig.6 (a-d). It is noted that due to continuous

impact of slurry on the samples there was the presence of corrosion pits on the surface of the samples. It is observed that corrosion pits are more on the substrate than the deposit in both 30° (Fig. 6 a-b) and 90° (Fig. 6 c-d). Number of corrosion pits is directly proportional to the weight loss. This is the main reason behind the weight loss of the samples after the test.

III.3. SEM results

Scanning electron micrograph of typical sand particles is shown in Figs. 7 a. Natural silica sand sieved to a nominal size range of 344 μm was used as an erodent. The average silica sand before test (size range of 220–500 μm) is shown in Fig.7 (a). It is noted that the size of the sand particles get reduced from nominal size range of 344 μm to 177 μm (Fig. 7 b). Due to continuous impingement of sand particles during testing the sand particle size get reduced.

Using scanning electron microscope, specimens tested at 30° and 90° were scanned on the surfaces at 250x magnifications and micrographs are shown in Figs.8 (a-d). The base metal is heavily eroded (Fig.8 a) when compared with the coated metal (Fig.8 b). The corrosion products are formed all over the surface of the base material (both in 90° and 30°) whereas in coated sample corrosion products are formed in selected area only. (Refer Fig. 8 (b&d)). The rough surfaces are indication of erosion. The white form or bright areas in the images shown above represent corrosion products. It is also noted that the corrosion products are more in 90° substrate samples compared with 90° friction surfaced deposit sample as shown in Fig.8 (c & d)

III.4 Pitting corrosion

Conjoint effect of erosion and corrosion behavior of friction surfaced and base metal of NAB alloy is presented in Figs.9 (a-d). From the pitting results typical polarization curves are generated for impact angles of 30° and 90° respectively. The respective I_{corr} value and rest potential are noted from the result generated by the software. It is noted that the Corrosion rate is increased in 90° samples compared with 30° samples. The corrosion rate of coated samples gets decreased compared with the base metal samples. The result generated by potentiostat is tabulated in Table.4.

TABLE 4
CORROSION PARAMETER OF SUBSTRATE AND DEPOSIT MATERIAL

Angle of impingement	Material	Rest potential (V)	I_{corr} (mA/cm ²)	Corrosion rate (mm/yr)
30°	Substrate	344.49381	0.0003433	0.3074438
30°	Deposit	407.14372	3.218E-05	0.0288237

90°	Substrate	543.07946	0.0073212	6.5573572
90°	Deposit	232.53697	1.932E-07	0.0001566

IV. Discussions

First, the granular microstructure of the NAB as given in fig.5a had a lower corrosion resistance than the finer counterpart. Ferrara and Catton described that the depth of attack in the cast NAB was powerfully influenced by the size and distribution of micro constituents, and the coarser microstructures caused in a deeper attack. The present result is in agreement with Ferraran and Caton's result [13]. The coarse microstructure resulted in the separation of elements specifically in the grain boundaries and this could deliver the corrosion path for the solution of preferentially corroded phases. FSP resulted in the breakup/decomposition of the coarse phases and the homogenization of elements as shown in fig 5c. This greatly eliminated the corrosion path, thereby enhancing the corrosion resistance.

Second, the cast porosities in the cast sample provided shortcuts for corrosion. On the one hand, these areas showed much lower corrosion resistance than the densified regions. On the other contrary, the porosities increased the area between the sample and the corrosion solution and this further hastened the corrosion process. However, FSP removed the porosities, and therefore increased the corrosion resistance effectively.

The values of impact angle were designated to identify the type of erosion mode shown by the coatings. Materials indicate low erosion rates at low angle of impingement (30°) fall in the category of materials, which displays ductile mode of erosion. On the other contrary, if the maximum erosion rate shown by material is at 90°, then it belongs to category of materials showing brittle mode [14]. From the erosion-corrosion test results, it is inferred that NAB showing brittle mode of erosion. From the optical micrographs, it is understood that as cast microstructure of substrate contains coarse grains whereas in deposits contain fine homogeneous microstructure. It is because of grain refinement by friction surfacing. This fine microstructure in deposits can be accomplished by stirring action of mechatrode with substrate [15].

The SEM study in Fig. 8 shows the NAB surface corrosion was first confined to the eutectoid regions with slight attack of the copper rich α -phase within the α +K_{III} eutectoid. While the eutectoid α -phase was preferentially attacked, the α -grains show very little attack; this is the form of selective phase corrosion. The accumulation of Cu₂O deposits at these portions will limit the diffusion (mass transport of species including: copper-ions, chloride and dissolved oxygen) towards and away from the NAB surface, thus there is the potential for a microenvironment to develop under the deposit. If the pH of this microenvironment becomes acidic, e.g. below pH 4.0, the K_{III} phase becomes anodic to the α -phase and corrodes preferentially. From the experimental results, it

is concluded that the fine grain structure is more preferential to achieve high strength and less prone to erosion corrosion. The cast NAB base material samples are mostly eroded and the corrosion products formed is more when compared to the friction surfaced samples

V. Conclusion

Slurry erosion-corrosion performance of friction surfaced extruded NAB alloy was investigated. Following conclusions are obtained from the present investigation.

1. Friction surfaced deposits are effective in controlling the slurry erosion of cast NAB alloy.
2. The friction surfaced extruded NAB alloy had much lower corrosion rate in the corrosion-erosion condition than the cast nickel-aluminum bronze alloy because of the microstructure such as the fine-tuning of grain size, removal of casting porosities.
3. The weight loss rate of both the substrate and deposits increased as the angle of impact increased from 30° to 90° .
4. At the localized sites, erosion corrosion happened because of the continuous nature of the K_{III} -phase and this resulted in the accumulation of corrosion.

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Fig.1 Friction surfaced sample (a) Deposition stage (b) Coating

Fig.2. Erosion corrosion test rig

Fig.3. Erosion corrosion samples (a) Base metal (b) Friction surfaced samples

Fig 4 Effect of impact angles in erosion rate [CM-Coated Metal, BM-Base Metal] (a) Mass Loss (b) Corrosion rate

Fig.5 Optical microstructures (a) base material-Cast NAB, (b) Mechatrode-Extruded NAB and (c) Friction surfacing

Fig.6 Optical microstructure of erosion corrosion (a) base metal at 30°, (b) base metal at 90° (c) Friction surfaced at 30° (d) Friction surfaced at 90°

Fig.7 Scanning electron micrograph of silica sand (a) before and (b) after erosion corrosion test

Fig.8 Effect of impact angle on erosion corrosion morphology (a) base metal in 30°, (b) coating at 30°, and (c) base metal at 90°, (d) coating at 90°

Fig. 9 Polarization curve for (a) 30°, friction surfaced (b) 30°, base metal (c) 90° friction surfaced (d) 90° base metal

